

Nadine Gordimer's "My Son's Story" as a Post-colonial Novel.

DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.17995745](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17995745)

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Date: 6 Aug 2021

Paper Name: African Literature

Paper code: MEN 402

Submitted to:

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MA English (4th Semester)

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Introduction

The term 'POSTCOLONIAL', designates any national literature written after the nation gained independence from a colonializing power. Postcolonial literature is the literature by people from formerly colonized countries. In terms of historical and chronological placement, "postcolonialism" is that state or condition which comes after the colonization process have come to a close; from this perspective, it is only possible to formulate the idea of a 'postcolonial state', after the end of the empire.

Postcolonial literature explores issues of cultural alienation, and it struggles to express the specificity and particularities of indigenous cultures in language that are not generally the original language of the indigenous people, but, rather the language of the former colonized. Some of the most prominent authors of postcolonial literature are Chinua Achebe, J. M. Coetzee, Franz Fanon, Nadine Gordimer, Jean Rhys, Derek Walcott, Salman Rushdie, etc. Though all these writers had different lands, nationalities and social backgrounds, they could all create their own distinction in producing wonderful works of literature, of which many would certainly come under the label 'postcolonial literature'. There are various, in terms of theories and conceptions. The postcolonial theorists examine both the colonial of the notable theorists who popularized colonialism such as Edward Fanon, Homi K. Bhabha and others. These theorists connected postcolonial literature with many fields like history, politics, philosophy and literary traditions and its significance in present day society. Postcolonial literature has many common motifs and themes like cultural dominance and racism, quest for identity, racial discrimination, inequality, hybridity along with some peculiar presentation styles.

Nadine Gordimer is one of the prominent authors of postcolonial literature. Gordimer is a towering figure of world literature. Gordimer was born in Springs, Transvaal, South Africa in 1923 and died in 2014. She is a writer of extraordinary power and acuity. Gordimer's writing deals with moral and racial issues, particularly apartheid in South Africa. Gordimer is a famous satirist and social reformer. Most of her novels are written for social change, reform, and for social ills, which is known as racism. In 1974 Gordimer won "Booker Prize" for 'The Conservationist' and in 1991 she won Nobel Prize for literature.

Postcolonial writer Nadine Gordimer in her novel 'My Son's Story' tells the tale of a family torn apart by illicit love, political struggle and apartheid. The novel is written in the apartheid era. In this novel, Gordimer transfers the narrative power to the son of a 'coloured' family so as to provide a new perspective of the marginalized. Her postcolonial stance lies in her deconstruction of social realities. Nadine Gordimer's tenth novel 'My Son's Story' deals with 'coloured' identity as deconstruction of racial categories and as a site of cultural transformation. The novel reveals around a 'coloured' family and a 'coloured' narrator. The focus on the 'coloured' family is significant precisely because the hybridity and instability of the term 'coloured' facilitate the kinds of shifts in identity and perception, that the narrative envisages.

The effect of Apartheid and Anti-Apartheid in The Novel “My Son’s Story”.

Anti-apartheid is one of the most important topics and a movement related to South Africa, when we speak about its postcolonial literature. South Africa was a nation in which a white legislature promulgated laws that made it impossible for the overwhelming majority of nonwhite persons to advance themselves, that happened in 1991, when the last of South Africans Apartheid

laws revealed. Apartheid, which in African means “*apartness*” was the law of the land. It became codified after the nationalist came to power in 1948. The system of Apartheid was one of the overwhelming oppressions in South Africa that engulfed each and every family of the society.

Apartheid made itself felt in the way writers in South Africa represented to the social and political situation around them. Writer like Nadine Gordimer who argued for the critical importance of giving politics a natural place in fiction rather than simply propagandizing in fiction. During the Apartheid years, Nadine Gordimer explains many complex aspects of human lives. In her novels, she highlighted on the specific consequences of the historical circumstances of life in South Africa, and she has for many years been a great keeper of the white South African.

The Novel “*My Son’s Story*” is the best manifestation of the hidden wounds of Apartheid. The story tells us of the effect of Apartheid on one black family in South Africa, and also the complexities of relationships between son, Will and his father, Sonny and his wife Aila, between Sonny and his lover Hannah, between everyone and the political situation at hand.

“Where his great grandfather or grandfather had come from nobody had recorded-the rough hands of those generations did not write letters or keep notes; brick-layers and carpenters, the only documentation of their lives was their work papers and the various, much folded slips entitling them to be employed in the town and to live in the area, outside the town, designated by the municipality for their kind.”

So, from these lines we can say that the “*white only*” policy Prohibited blacks from holding many jobs; they were not allowed to ran business or professional practices in any areas designated for whites only.

Nadine Gordimer exposes both the protagonist and narrator, Sonny and will respectively, from coloured identity set in the atmosphere of racial separation, when apartheid in South Africa was getting infamous. The major protagonist, resisting the apartheid in South Africa is caught up in interracial affair with a white woman, Hannah plowman who is an anti- apartheid activist.

Here Gordimer insightfully shows some of the paradoxes of white involvement in this cause, as Hannah’s love for a black African man endangers both of them and the movement.

In contrast, Gordimer exposes the different history of blacks and whites’ relationship during the apartheid by presenting the alternative relationship between black and white.

Sonny who is a colored school teacher who is slowly drawn into the struggle against the white regime. Sonny tries to adjust both into the revolution and struggle against segregation, on the

other hand has warm relationship with white, in an individual level. Later his family discovers the affair and are themselves drawn into the fight against apartheid.

Furthermore, female characters too undergo through the abrupt transformation from their confined space home to politics. To be precise, Aila, a silent house wife to Sonny, after being known sonny's affair with Hannah, suddenly decides to take part in ongoing revolution to overcome the white racist regime.

In similar way, Baby, a daughter is also caught up by revolutionary attempt to throw white regime and eventually join the resistance group to fight against apartheid laws. Likewise, the characters from the mixed or black race build the emotional attachment with white characters and vice versa.

The fact that Sonny and many others, had to fight for the liberty of their people and then spent time in jail for it, and it also highlights the fate of black south Africans. The unfairness of apartheid is further highlighted by the fact that the family is unwelcome in the white neighborhood of Johannesburg into which they move.

Gordimer very skillfully present a real picture of African family in this novel. Furthermore, Gordimer tries to expose socio-political situation in South Africa. To paraphrase, one might say politics is a character in South Africa. The racial segregation and discrimination, which is in large scale, throughout the country, also has its manifestation in Sonny's family which has ravaged all family relationships, thereby disintegrating the bond of love among them.

The author depicts the picture of South Africa during the state of emergency white supremacist ideologies used in this novel.

As narrator Will, in the very beginning of the story admits what it meant to be black in South Africa, as line goes,

"Cinemas had been open to us only a year or so; it was double freedom I look; to bunk study and sit in the maroon nylon velvet seat of a cinema where white live".

Here, we can see the discrimination in South Africa along with the counter point that what happens when two races are banned to be together in the public places, as the narrator, as a child, bunk the class not only to watch the movie, but also to feel what it means to remain in the seat where white lives. So, Gordimer exposes several aspects of discrimination against black and non-white in the nation.

Moreover, Gordimer deconstruct the very discourse constructed by the white regime discourse presents black as lazy, unintelligent and inferior, I contrast she depicts black character as intelligent and educated smart enough to write their own history.

However, even in extreme age of apartheid the black characters find white characters as a need. Gordimer subtly tries to assure black, that time is changing gradually. Moreover, she tries to persuade that separated blacks and white should try to build the bond between each other. Black character is depicted as someone to make journey through the new space where black and white come together, more subtly, Gordimer suggests the fact that black people as the people to go through the new experience of equality and freedom as the demand of postapartheid.

Hybridity

“Hybridity” is a very important theme found in “My Son’s Story”. And it is also one of the important features found in post-colonial literature. As a term, the ‘Concept of Hybridity’ has its origination from biology. In biology, the term hybrid is the result i.e., offspring, from combining the qualities of two organisms of different breeds, varieties, species through the process of reproduction. And in general term, we can say, it is a blend or mixture of two different things.

(4)

As time passed by, Literature, Sociology and Cultural Studies etc also got influenced by it. These fields included this term to interpret their own ideologies. But, the basic origin of the meaning, till date remains the same.

We can link hybridization to the terms such as globalization, multiculturalism and multiracialism. And it is a result of close study, to find linkage between these terms. Due to hybridization, we can see the transformation linguistically, culturally, politically, racially etc. These terms seem to promote globalization yet can and maybe controversial to quite an extent. From an old and traditional cultural standpoint, we can find the decrease of the essence of its originality in terms of culture, due to which it may seem unconventional.

In postcolonial context, hybridity may actually mean mixing and intermingling of the colonizer and the colonized. To be more specific, we can bring the reference of ‘eastern’ and ‘western’ culture. Eastern and western terms are culturally and politically constructed one, based on mindset or region. And to great extent, it seems controversial.

When we study hybridity in association with the novel “My Son’s Story” we can see various glimpse of hybridization. We can find two aspects of hybridity i.e., negative and positive aspects of hybridity. For instance, *“The boy was the first in the family to leave earth, cement, wood and kapok behind and take up the pen and book. He was the first to complete the full years of schooling. Sonny became a teacher. He was the pride of the old people and the generic diminutive by which they had celebrated him as the son, the first-born male, was to stay with him in the changing identities a man passes through, for the rest of his life.”* (My Son’s Story)

From the above extract, we can find hybridity in mindset. In this context, we can say that colonialism resulted in hybridity. We can refer this hybridity to education and accepting it mentally, in its newest form. We can consider it to be a positive aspect of hybridity. When we read and observe the history of colonialism, we can find that education was one of the primary aspects of colonialism. Colonizers wanted the colonized people to adopt their religion through education and improve the economic condition of colonizers. We can say, it is the negative aspect of hybridity. From the colonized standpoint, we can say that British education system was primarily based on politics and religion i.e., Christianity in particular. But the essence of their education system took its turn and diverted to some of the good reforms that were formed. To be more precise, we can take the instance from the above extract. We can find the character,

Sonny, was from working class background, but, his education made him enjoy and achieve a new status in the society. Here the author states that he was “*the first in the family to leave earth, cement, wood and kapok behind and take up pen and book*” and he was also “*the pride of the old people.*”

(5)

“*The pride of the old people*” gives us the picture of the old people accepting British form of education and feeling proud of their children’s achievements in the field of education.

Apart from general hybridity that was previously pointed out, we can also find ‘racial hybridity’. It is a term which refers to cross racial mixing of different races. In the novel, *My Son’s Story* we can find initial progress of racial hybridity. To make this statement clearer, let us take the example of illicit relationship of Hannah Plowman and Sonny of this novel.

“*...my father and a woman came out of the earlier performance in another.*” (*My Son’s Story*) --- I

“*She is blonde, my father’s woman.*” (*My Son’s Story*) --- II

“Sonny read and reread them with devotion; although the gilt lettering had been eaten away by fishmoth, and the volume he wanted had to be selected blindly, his hand always

went straight to it.” (*My Son’s Story*) --- III

The above extracted lines from the novel give us a clear picture of coloured and white race intermingling with one another, on the ground of extra marital affair. Here Hannah is described as blonde which gives us the image of a white woman, in terms of physical description. If we see the past history of Africa, we can find commonalities in thought, relationship or approaches.

But colonialism resulted in crossing the racial boundaries. It was also followed in postcolonial era as well, as portrayed in the novel. The third extract given above i.e., the admiration for literary works of Shakespeare, can be said to be the result of hybridity. The literary works of Shakespeare has its origin in United Kingdom and regionally related to colonizers. But, Sonny instead of hating his works, read and admired his works. Even Will, his son’s name was inspired by Shakespeare, and called in a shortened form. And through this, we can say colonialism resulted in different types of hybridity such as racial, linguistic, cultural and even political hybridity.

Women challenging the conventional norms in post-colonial era in South Africa.

We all know that women have always been overruled by patriarchal society. But in this context, South African women in particular are to be focused. Men had greater role even in South African society. So, women were always shown and said to be engaging primarily in domestic works. It included giving birth to their children, feeding and taking care of the whole family and doing the entire household works. They were always confined to their house works and were never expected to engage themselves in legal, political or any other matters which were not related to their house. Women engaging in economic activity were not accepted openly, if this activity, surpassed their so-called criteria. 'So-called criteria' are rules constructed for women by

their society. But, it was somewhat acceptable, if they did this to feed their children or earn their living as shown in the novel.

“She, too, had matriculated, but she had married from the close female domain of her parents’ home at eighteen, and never worked in the world. He did not want a bed-and-board wife and she wanted to become what he wanted, so she took a secretarial course and studied psychology by correspondence as preparation for a useful working life.” (My Son’s Story)

From the above extracted lines from the novel, we can find how African women were also gradually embracing education. Aila is described as a woman who have taken secretarial course and even studied psychology by correspondence for useful working life. This gives us the picture of a South African woman starting to be independent and self-reliant. Even Sonny is described as a man who supported women to pursue their education and career. This acceptance of education by women were not a rapid one, but, the gradual change in outlook made many African women to fight against injustice. Engagement of such intellectual women in movements for independence such as anti-apartheid was a credit.

Though the characters such as Aila and Baby are fictional African-women characters, we can find how their roles are very prominent one. Aila and Baby is also described as engaging in Anti-apartheid struggle.

“Her name would be honoured, from now on, in the movement inside and outside the country—where she could still be active” (My Son’s Story)

The lines given above are descriptions about Aila. At the beginning, she is shown as a woman who was calm, gentle, and feminine according to the society, but, gradual change in her identity made her a revolutionary woman. We can find her, gradually challenging the conventional norms constructed for women of African society. Her sudden change in character and personality was accepted and celebrated by the people of her country. This acceptance makes us feel that men were also gradually starting to support women to find their own identity, in the post-colonial era.

Even the character of Hannah Plowman is influential, if we exclude the context of black or coloured women. She is shown engaging in legal matters, organizations and even in politics indirectly.

*“Hannah Plowman, representative of an international human rights organization”
(My Son’s Story) --- I*

“The United Nations High Commission for Refugees wanted her to take on a high-level post. She hadn’t applied for it—she wouldn’t have

*(7) thought of changing jobs while she was fortunate enough” (My Son’s Story) -
-- II*

*“Hannah Plowman, she’s great— And someone interrupted:
—But she’s not here any longer, man. She’s got some fancy job with the
UN High Commission for Refugees,” (MY Son’s Story) ---
III*

The above stages of extracted lines are about Hannah Plowman. She is said to be a representative of human rights organization on an international level. Later we can also find, that UN’s high commission for refugees also referred her to take high post. And later we can find someone speaking about Hannah’s new job in the same organization. From these instances, we can find, how privileged, a White woman was, as compared to black or coloured woman. But her hardship and struggle of being a successful and independent woman in a male dominated world is of massive appreciation. If we see the similarities of coloured, black and white women, we can find that education is one of the most important sources which can set a similar and independent stage for them. But the only difference that we see, is the level of opportunity, that is given for women i.e., coloured and black women in particular, in the postcolonial era.

Conclusion

Thus, all the previously mentioned features and elements make “My Son’s Story” a postcolonial novel. The presence of anti-apartheid, hybridity and women of South Africa in post-colonial era, helps in exploring the different sites of postcolonialism. Postcolonial literature is a very vast form of literature. Each colonized nation and its literature have their own interesting way of showcasing the economic, political and social realities of the era. Similarly, “My Son’s Story” also explores the dark realities of colonialism and the effects that it created in social, political as well as personal level. We can find a vast distinction based on physical appearance, complexion, gender and social status. The novel showcases how every character tries to reveal the harsh regime of the white rulers. The novel, in a way tries to present a new form of history to the world, that is completely different as interpreted by the colonizers. Even today, there are many cases, where we find discrimination on the grounds of race, ethnicity and social background etc, even after independence. So, in general, we can say that, literature is a very important source, through which one can expose the bitter realities of life and step further towards better foundations of developments.